

Trivalent transition metal ion directed macrocycles

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Trivalent chromium, manganese and iron salts react *in situ* with 2,6-diacetylpyridine and 1,2-diaminobenzene to form complexes containing a 18-membered N₆ tetradentate macrocyclic ligand. The complexes are of distorted octahedral type [M(TML)]X₃, where M = Cr^{III}, Mn^{III} or Fe^{III} and X = Cl, Br, NO₃ or NCS for Cr^{III} and Fe^{III}; and X = OAc for Mn^{III}, TML = tetradentate macrocyclic ligand. The ligand coordinates through all the six nitrogen atoms. The complexes behave as 1 : 3 electrolytes and the test for anions are positive, indicate their presence outside the coordination sphere.

Metal complexes with synthetic macrocyclic ligands are of great importance, in part because of their resemblance with many natural systems, e.g., porphyrins and cobalamines. The publications of several review articles and books covering various aspects of synthetic macrocyclic ligands reveal the great importance attached to them¹⁻³. Most of the metal chelates have been derived from aliphatic or aromatic diamines and aliphatic dicarbonyl compounds. However, no work has been reported on the metal complexes of macrocyclic compounds derived from aromatic dicarbonyl and aromatic diamines. In our previous paper, we have reported bivalent nickel, cobalt and copper complexes of N₆ macrocyclic ligand⁴, and as an extension of this work, trivalent chromium, manganese, and iron chelates are reported here.

Results and discussion

The analytical data of metal chelates favour their general

composition as [M(C₃₀H₂₆N₆)]X₃, where M = Cr^{III}, Mn^{III} or Fe^{III} and X = Cl, Br, NO₃ or NCS for Cr^{III} and Fe^{III} and OAc for Mn^{III}. The molar conductance values (Table 1) in DMF classify them as 1 : 3 electrolytes⁵ and the test for anions are positive directly, indicating their presence out of the co-ordination sphere.

Infrared spectra :

The IR spectra of all the complexes do not exhibit any NH₂ bands in the region ~3400–3200 cm⁻¹. There is no band at ~1700 cm⁻¹ due to the free carbonyl group⁴. The absence of stretching and bending vibrations of the (C–O) group at ~1525 and 1280 cm⁻¹ substantiate the absence of this group⁶. The strong band appearing as doublets, ~1595–1629 cm⁻¹ may be assigned to ν(C=N) vibrations and point towards the co-ordination through the azomethine group⁷. Therefore, it is clear from the IR spectra that both the NH₂ groups of 1,2-diaminobenzene have condensed with both the carbonyl groups of 2,6-diacetylpyridine to give rise to

Table 1. Analytical data of trivalent chromium, manganese and iron complexes*

Compd.	Colour	ΛMhos cm ⁻² mol ⁻¹	Mol. Wt.	Decomposition temp.
[Cr(C ₃₀ H ₂₆ N ₆)]Cl ₃	Green	205	628.5	255d
[Cr(C ₃₀ H ₂₆ N ₆)]Br ₃	Green	209	752	270d
[Cr(C ₃₀ H ₂₆ N ₆)](NO ₃) ₃	Green	219	698	290d
[Cr(C ₃₀ H ₂₆ N ₆)](NCS) ₃	Green	212	686	260d
[Mn(C ₃₀ H ₂₆ N ₆)](OAc) ₃	Brown	211	696	310d
[Fe(C ₃₀ H ₂₆ N ₆)]Cl ₃	Brown	224	632.5	280d
[Fe(C ₃₀ H ₂₆ N ₆)]Br ₃	Red	229	766	320d
[Fe(C ₃₀ H ₂₆ N ₆)](NO ₃) ₃	Brown	228	712	330d

*All compounds gave satisfactory C, H, N and metal analyses.

Table 2. Magnetic and electronic spectral data of trivalent chromium and manganese complexes

Compd*	Spectral bands (cm ⁻¹)	Dq	Dt	DT	DQ	DT/DQ	μ _{eff} B.M. (300 K)
[Cr(TML)]Cl ₃	17150, 21100, 25750, 29250	2110	451	6110	50790	0.13	3.67
[Cr(TML)]Br ₃	16850, 20850, 25900, 29400	2085	458	6190	50103	0.13	3.62
[Cr(TML)](NO ₃) ₃	16700, 21400, 25650, 29100	2140	538	7275	50235	0.14	3.70
[Cr(TML)](NCS) ₃	17100, 21250, 26150, 29010	2125	475	6425	50235	0.12	3.76
[Mn(TML)](OAc) ₃	13450, 17550, 20800	1755	469	6340	40758	0.15	4.88

*TML = Tetradentate macrocyclic ligand.

N₆ arrangement of four azomethine and two pyridine nitrogen atoms equally suitable for coordination. 2,6-Disubstituted pyridine derivatives show various bands in the regions at ~1585–1615, 1570–1590, 1455–1490 and 1440–1445 cm⁻¹, can be assigned to four ν(C=C) skeletal frequencies and designated as bands I, II, III and IV of pyridine ring, respectively⁷⁻⁹. The two strong bands ~785 and 740 cm⁻¹ are assigned to Φ(C-H) and Φ(C-C) vibrations, respectively¹⁰.

The spectra of the chelates exhibit a downward shift in the location of bands I, II, III and IV. The band at 990 cm⁻¹ disappear and are replaced by a band appearing at ~1015–1025 cm⁻¹. The band assigned to Ψ(C-C) splits into two, ~725 and 740 cm⁻¹, while Ψ(C-H) appears at ~785 cm⁻¹ as a single band. These changes point towards the involvement of the pyridine-nitrogen co-ordination. Furthermore, the bands assignable to an in-plane (C-C) deformation (~605 cm⁻¹) and an out-of-plane (C-C) deformation (~410 cm⁻¹) undergo an upward shift to 15–20 cm⁻¹ in the spectra of chelates, which is consistent with the coordination of pyridine-nitrogen to the metal atom¹¹. This mode of coordination is further supported by the far-IR spectra of complexes.

In the spectra of the complexes under study, a strong band at ~1625 cm⁻¹ with a shoulder at ~1645 cm⁻¹ may be assigned to symmetric and antisymmetric stretching mode of azomethine linkage¹² and the frequency concerned with the ν(C=N) stretching mode shifted to lower range by 15–20 cm⁻¹, with a marginal loss of the intensity of the band. This lowering may be taken as an indication of the co-ordination of the nitrogen of the azomethine group to the metal atom⁶. The appearance of three bands at ~1350, 1230 and 825 cm⁻¹ assignable to NO₂ asymmetric stretching, symmetric stretching and bending modes, respectively, are found in the nitrate complexes. The fact is further substantiated by the presence of a sharp narrow band at ~1675 cm⁻¹ in these complexes, suggesting the ionic nature of nitrate group. The weak bands at ~2370 cm⁻¹ and another strong band at ~2110 cm⁻¹ are depicted by the thiocyanato complexes of

the metals. The bands are due to ν(C=N) of NCS group and suggest the ionic nature of thiocyanato group¹³.

The acetato complex of Mn^{III} shows new bands at ~1570 and 1410 cm⁻¹ assignable to antisymmetric and symmetric ν(COO) vibrations of ionic acetate¹⁴. Thus, it is evident that acetate is present in ionic form in this complex.

Magnetic and electronic spectral studies :

Chromium complexes :

The magnetic moment values of chromium(III) complexes lie in the range 3.60–3.76 B.M. (Table 2) at RT (300 K), corresponding to three unpaired electrons.

The solution spectra of chromium complexes exhibit bands at 16700–17150 (ν₁), 20850–21,400 (ν₂), 25650–26150 (ν₃) and 29010–29400 cm⁻¹ (ν₄), respectively. By assuming the effective geometry to be D_{4h}, various bands may be assigned to : 4B_{1g} → 4E_g (a) ; 4B_{1g} → 4B_{2g} ; 4B_{1g} → 4E_g (b) and 4B_{1g} → 4A_{2g}, respectively in the following order of increasing energy. Therefore, first two bands are the splits of the band designated as 2T_{2g} and the other two bands are splits of the band 2T_{1g} in quadrature fields¹⁵. The value of various radial parameters Dq and Dt are calculated by employing various energy level equations¹⁶.

Manganese complex :

The magnetic moment value of Mn^{III} acetate complex is 4.88 B.M. at RT (300 K) and is indicative of a high-spin d⁴ system¹⁷.

The solution spectra of Mn^{III} complex shows bands at ~13450, 17550, 20800 and 33510 cm⁻¹. High-spin Mn^{III} complexes are expected to give one d-d transition due to severe Jahn-Teller distortion in d⁴ metal complexes¹⁸. The relevant ligand field transitions for high-spin d⁴ systems are : d_{z²} → d_{x²-y²} ; d_{xz,yz} → d_{x²-y²} and d_{xz} → d_{x²-y²}, respectively in increasing order of energy. The first band at ~13450 cm⁻¹ assignable to 5B_{1g} → 5E_g transition is the most convincing evidence for D_{4h} symmetry. The other bands can be assigned to : 5B_{1g} → 5B_{2g} and 5B_{1g} → 5E_g; transitions, respectively. The higher energy band ~33510

cm^{-1} in the complex may be assigned to a π - π^* charge transfer transition due to azomethine linkage.

Iron complexes :

The magnetic moment values of iron(III) complexes at RT (300 K) lie in the range 5.76–5.84 B.M. The values are slightly lower than the values expected for spin-free iron complexes. However, the values are well within the range reported for high-spin, six co-ordinate iron(III) complexes⁹.

The solution spectra of iron(III) complexes show well discernable absorption bands in the regions 17500–18500, 19800 and 24650–24950 cm^{-1} . The lower energy bands at ~17500 and 19800 cm^{-1} are probably due to splitting of $4T_{1g}$ term and points towards the distorted nature of these complexes. The various bands can be assigned to : ${}^6A_{1g} \rightarrow 4T_{1g} ({}^4E)$; ${}^6A_{1g} \rightarrow 1T_{1g} ({}^4A_2)$; ${}^6A_{1g} \rightarrow 4T_{2g}$; transitions, respectively. The band at higher region ~33575 cm^{-1} is of charge-transfer nature. The appearance of the lower energy absorption bands at ~ 17500 and 24650 cm^{-1} suggest that these complexes are distorted octahedral and conforming to D_{4h} geometry¹⁸.

Far-infrared spectra :

The far-IR spectra of the present complexes show various new bands assignable to metal-pyridine and metal-nitrogen (azomethine) vibrations. The new bands appear in the spectra of chromium (248–250 cm^{-1}), manganese (250 cm^{-1}) and iron (255 cm^{-1}), complexes may be due to $\nu(\text{Cr-N})$, $\nu(\text{Mn-N})$ and $\nu(\text{Fe-N})$ metal-pyridine vibrations modes, respectively.

The spectra of these complexes show another bands in the regions ~410 and 590 cm^{-1} assignable to (C–C) out-of-plane and (C–C) in-plane deformations region. These vibrations experience significant shift towards higher frequency region and again point towards the coordination of pyridine-nitrogen to the metal ion¹⁹. The spectra of the complexes also exhibit various bands in the regions : 460–475, 300–315 and 325–330 cm^{-1} and may be tentatively assigned to : $\nu(\text{Cr-N})$, $\nu(\text{Mn-N})$, and $\nu(\text{Fe-N})$ azomethine vibrations, respectively¹⁹.

Experimental

All the chemicals and reagents used were of AnalaR grade. 2,6-Diacetylpyridine (Aldrich) was used. All the physico-chemical studies and analyses were performed as reported earlier⁴.

Chromium and iron complexes :

A mixture of methanolic solution (100 cm^3) each of 2,6-diacetylpyridine (~0.02 mol) and 1,2-diaminobenzene (0.02 mol) was refluxed for 2 h. To it the metal salt (0.01 mol)

dissolved in minimum amount of methanol was added, followed by 2–3 drops of glacial acetic acid and refluxing continued for 6–8 h. The solution was then concentrated to half of its volume and kept in desiccator for 3 days. The dark coloured crystals that separated were dried at 110° in an oven (yield ~35%).

The complexes of nitrates were synthesized from metal nitrates. Bromide and thiocyanate complexes were prepared by adding KBr and NH_4NCS , respectively to the methanolic solutions of metal chlorides and filtering off the precipitates of KCl and NH_4Cl .

Manganese complex :

Manganese(III) acetate was prepared by the standard method²⁰. A mixture of methanolic solution (100 cm^3) each of 1-2-diaminobenzene (~0.02 mol) and 2,6-diacetylpyridine (~0.02 mol) was refluxed for 3 h. To it manganese(III) acetate (0.01 mol) dissolved in methanol (30 cm^3) was added, followed by 2–3 drops of glacial acetic acid and refluxing continued for 8 h. The solution was then concentrated to half its volume and kept in desiccator for 3 days. The dark coloured crystals separated were dried at 110° in an oven, yield ~35%.

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